

Original Article

Lower Back Pain in the students at a Local Institute and its Correlation with Smoking and Gender

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ABSTRACT

Background: Lower back pain (LBP) not only remains the foremost cause of work absence and medical consultation but is also the leading cause of disability. It affects individuals from both the developed and developing countries including children, adolescents, and elderly. The aim of this research was to investigate the correlation between risk factors such as gender, smoking, and occupation and lower back pain among the people of Pakistan. The findings will be useful to establish factors associated with the condition and those can be modified to better manage the pain. **Methodology :** A questionnaire based on cross sectional study which was conducted at a local medical college constituting both the students and the staff. **Results:** Prevalence of LBP was 51%. Males reported a higher frequency of LBP as compared to females ($r=.191$, $p=0.03$). LBP was also associated with occupation. Students had a higher incidence of LBP ($r=.178$, $p=0.04$) as compared to the non-students (i.e., staff). Smoking was also associated with LBP as smokers showed significantly higher frequency of LBP ($r=.366$, $p=0.006$). Greater Frequency of LBP was also linked with higher grade of pain ($r=0.346$, $p=0.005$). Females reported a higher grade of pain as compared to males ($r=0.292$, $p=0.01$). **Conclusion :** There is a high frequency of LBP in students associated with gender, smoking and lifestyle. Proper education and planning are needed to address the situation. More prospective studies are indicated to further validate the results of this study.

Keywords: Lower Back Pain, Smoking, Students, Gender, Correlation

Introduction

Low back pain (LBP) is a public health problem which is emerging all over the world. There are some general assumptions that lower back pain and weight are related.¹ But scientific evidence is still not supporting this relation fully.²⁻⁴ Some studies have reported that lower back pain is due to different postures to counterbalance the excessive abdominal fat.⁵ It is also observed that height and low back pain are also related. The height is linked to lower back pain.⁶ Lower back pain may be due to large abdominal fat mass and may increase lower back pain linked with bending in people with large abdominal fat mass or large waist.⁵ When they are walking downstairs or bending forward for lifting, to overcome the gravitational pull-on fat mass, more reactive forces are required so that they can balance themselves. As a result of this lower back feels more strain.⁵ Some studies have proved that people with high waist to hip ratio, which is central fat distribution, are at higher risk of low back pain and it is independent of total fat which can be measured by body mass index. However, other evidence of height and lower back pain is conflicting. Studies were reported that there was no association between low back pain and height even after age and lifestyle adjustments.^{5,6} But, a study reported that women above 170 cm and the men above 180 cm had 4- and 2-times risk of herniated lumbar intervertebral disc as compared to the 10cm shorter people.⁸ On the other hand another study done previously did not find any association between lower back pain and height.⁹

In addition, many studies have reported a stronger association between back pain and social class.¹⁰ In the occurrence of non-fatal conditions, social class differences such as back pain may provide clues to etiology, but data is very limited about these. There are certain occupational factors that have been linked with back pain among low socio-economic status include the manual lifting of heavyweights.¹¹ Cigarette smoking,¹² stress and psychiatric morbidity are some of the evidences which link backache with behaviours which vary across social

groupings.¹³ Although this evidence related to these risks is far from consistent,⁹ it provides the basis for interpreting socio-economic differences in back pain occurrence. However, these earlier studies on the association of socio-economic influences and lower back pain among women have not considered type of delivery, sterilization and other reproductive history which may confound the results.

We thus aimed in this research to investigate the link between such factors of risk and lower back pain among the people of Pakistan. The findings will help us establish a conclusion as to which factor contributes most to making a person vulnerable to developing back ache.

Methodology

A cross-sectional study was conducted at a local Medical College, following the approval of Ethical Review Committee. The estimated sample size was 100 individuals in accordance with the formula, $n = Z^2 * P(1-P) / m^2$ (confidence interval of 95% and error margin of 5%). Random sampling was done, and 108 participants were taken and collected their informed consent.

The data collected will be analyzed using SPSS version 25. A chi-square test was performed for determining relation of lower back pain with other items. Descriptive Statistics and Pearson's Correlation Test were applied and a value of $p \leq 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results

A total of 108 people responded to the survey. Out of which 77 (71%) participants were female and 31 (29%) were male. 78% of the participants were 17-25 years of age. Students represented 38% (41) of the total study population. Height ranged from 4'5'' to 7'5''. Weight of the participants ranged from 42 kg to 83kg. 92% of our study population were non-smokers and 58.3% had the educational status 'Undergraduate'.

Table 1: Summary of statistically significant correlations in the study

Variables	Significance	P value
Gender and LBP	.191	0.03
Occupation and LBP	.178	0.04
Smoking and LBP	.366	0.006
Frequency of LBP and Grade of Pain	.346	0.005
Gender and Grade of Pain	.292	0.01

A summary of statistically significant correlations found in the study is given in the **Table 1**. LBP was associated with 'being a female', 'being a student', and 'being a smoker'. Greater frequency of pain was associated with a higher grade of pain. Furthermore, females reported a higher grade of pain as compared to males.

Discussion

This study reveals some significant correlations of LBP in young adults. Almost half of the students reported lower back pain. This might be due to modified lifestyle of the students. Stress and sedentary lifestyle have been associated with LBP.¹³ which might be a reason of this finding.

The study shows a higher frequency and grade of pain in females as compared to males. Females due to hormonal variations are at higher risk of experiencing pain.¹⁴, thus there is a need of proper education for females toward LBP and its management.

Smoking was also significantly associated with pain. A 'dose-response' relationship between smoking and LBP has been reported in previous studies as well.¹⁰ Biologically plausible explanations of the link between smoking and back pain, a study of this correlation has been done by Ernst in which he discussed the effect of smoking on nutrition.¹⁰

A higher frequency of LBP was associated with a higher grade of pain which means that recurrent Low Back Pain can be increasing in grade. It

signifies the need of proper management of pain from the inception.

Females experienced a higher grade of pain as compared to males. This has been reported in previous studies as well.¹⁵

Limitations of this study include a limited sample size and self-reported questionnaire. Further prospective studies and large-scale surveys are indicated to further validate these results.

Conclusion

We conclude that LBP is associated with smoking, gender and lifestyle. This situation can be addressed by proper education, planning and management. More prospective studies are indicated to further validate the study's results.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Contributions of the Authors

MSQ, KZ devised the plan
AUH, AI wrote the manuscript
UA, IA did overall supervision
AUH, AI repharsed and did statistical analyses

